

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF WRAPPED COMPOSITE X-JOINTS UNDER MONOTONIC UNIAXIAL AND MULTI-AXIAL LOAD CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Wrapped composite joints excel as an alternative to welded joints, exhibiting superior static and fatigue performance. This paper presents an experimental investigation into the failure mechanisms and load-bearing capacity of wrapped composite joints under multi-axial monotonic loading. The study aims to explore the effectiveness of wrapped composite joints in resisting multi-axial loads and gain insight into failure modes. Results reveal exceptional resistance to uniaxial tension, bending, and multi-axial tension+bending. Failure modes include interfacial debonding, delamination, composite fracture, and steel yielding. Strain monitoring via Digital Image Correlation (DIC) and embedded optical fibers confirms these findings, highlighting significant multi-axial loading resistance.

KEYWORDS

Wrapped Composite Joint; X-Joints; Debonding; Multi-axial loads; Failure modes; Circular hollow section (CHS)

INTRODUCTION

Circular hollow section (CHS) X-joints find wide application in offshore multi-membered structures, such as wind turbine foundations, where they are subjected to multi-axial loads from wind and wave forces. Traditional welded connections introduce stress concentrations, necessitating the use of stubs and cans to reinforce the joints (Sandal et al., 2018). However, recent research by Feng and Pavlovic (2021) has demonstrated a significant improvement in fatigue life, up to 10-100 times, by utilizing a fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composite wrap to connect CHS structures without welding, thereby reducing the reliance on stubs and cans.

Previous studies have predominantly focused on investigating the static performance of wrapped composite joints under uniaxial tension, compression, and in-plane bending, revealing their superior stiffness and ultimate load-bearing capacity compared to welded joints (He & Pavlovic, 2022). However, in the context of jacket foundation structures for offshore wind turbines, it is imperative to extend our understanding to the behavior of joints under multi-axial load conditions. These structures encounter diverse loading scenarios, including axial forces and bending moments, stemming from wind, waves, and tides. The response of jacket joints to these multi-axial loading conditions significantly influences the overall structural integrity and reliability of the system. Therefore, gaining comprehensive insights into the behavior and performance of joints subjected to these complex load combinations is essential for the safe and efficient design of wrapped composite joints.

This conference paper presents experimental results on wrapped medium-scale 90° X-joints, featuring a CHS diameter of $\phi 168.3 \times 12.5$ mm. The joints were subjected to various load configurations, including monotonic uniaxial tension, uniaxial bending out and in-plane, axial tension + bending out-of-plane, and axial tension + bending out-of-plane + bending in-plane. Through this comprehensive experimental investigation, the study successfully identifies failure modes and their interaction under different load conditions. The results demonstrate the exceptional resistance of the wrapped joints, surpassing the yield resistance of the CHS with consistent debonding observed at the steel-FRP

interface as the primary failure mode. These findings demonstrate the robust performance of the wrapped joints, even under multi-axial loading conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF MULTI-AXIAL BEHAVIOR

The testing of X-joints in various load directions and configurations, representative of offshore structures, presents challenges in terms of feasibility and cost. To address this, medium-scale X-joints, scaled at 1/3.6 of the actual size, are designed considering the limitations of the test equipment in terms of geometry and ultimate load capacity.

In the ongoing phase of innovation related to wrapped composite joints, the main emphasis lies in investigating the debonding phenomenon occurring at the interface between the steel and FRP wrap. Extensive efforts are made to carefully select load configurations and proportions to ensure that existing prediction models accurately capture significant debonding as a critical failure mechanism. These prediction models currently incorporate calibrated Cohesive Zone Models (CZM) based on uniaxial experiments, which are employed to represent the interfacial behavior between FRP and steel.

The objective of the experimental campaign is to collect data for the calibration and validation of finite element models (FEM) specifically designed for wrapped joints under multi-axial loading conditions. Furthermore, the campaign aims to establish interaction criteria for various multi-axial load configurations. By conducting experiments and gathering comprehensive data, researchers seek to enhance the accuracy and reliability of FEM predictions when dealing with wrapped joints subjected to multi-axial loading.

Specimen configuration

The medium-scale 90° wrapped X-joints, depicted in Figure 2a, are designed based on a full-scale 90° wrapped X-joint used in a representative jacket design case study. The medium-scale factor of 1/3.6 is determined by considering the maximum specimen length and ultimate load capacity of various test equipment employed in the testing campaign. Machined flanges are utilized to secure the specimens in the test equipment at the end of the brace sections. These flanges undergo full penetration butt welding and are meticulously smoothed both internally and externally. The incorporation of flanges enables the application of all necessary load conditions to the joint.

At the current stage of development, the wrapped joint design primarily emphasizes ultimate limit failure, specifically limited debonding at the steel-FRP interface under static design load levels. This design approach enhances the joint's fatigue performance, resulting in higher fatigue resistance compared to the fatigue resistance of the CHS. To prevent early fatigue failure of the circumferential weld, the steel thickness of the CHS is increased from 4mm (corresponding to the D/t ratio of the full-scale joint) to 12.5mm. An additional experiment is conducted to validate the fatigue performance of the circumferential weld, confirming that the fatigue life exceeds the intended number of test cycles.

The final design comprises $\phi 168.3 \times 12.5$ mm CHS with a brace wrapping length of $1.5 \times D$ and a chord wrapping length of $1.0 \times D$, as illustrated in Figure 2b. The wrap thickness exhibits a maximum thickness of 55mm at the joint root (the furthest distance from the root to the composite surface), an average thickness of 20mm at the brace sections, and a thickness of 0mm at the wrapping end. No post-curing is applied to the joints during production. The alignment of the steel sections is achieved temporarily using a two-component, toughened, methacrylate structural adhesive. Prior to wrapping, the CHS undergo a process of grit blasting and degreasing to facilitate a strong interfacial bond between the steel and FRP. Meticulous attention is given to ensure that all specimens possess similar roughness properties, thereby maintaining consistency in the surface characteristics.

Figure 1 a). Photo medium-scale 90° X-joint; b). Dimensions medium-scale 90° X-joints.

Experimental set-up and Instrumentation

The experimental campaign employs two distinct setups. Uniaxial experiments are conducted using a custom 2.5MN tensile frame, specifically designed to accommodate the testing requirements, see Figure 2a. This frame has a height of 6 meters and facilitates the application of uniaxial loads. For bending and multi-axial tests, a 6-degree-of-freedom (DOF) machine known as the "Hexapod" is utilized, see figure Figure 2c. The Hexapod provides the necessary flexibility and control to perform these types of tests accurately. The Hexapod is capable of applying a combination of 1000kN axial load, 400kN of shear, and 400kNm of bending.

To capture strain data in the vicinity of the interface, embedded optical fibers are employed across all loading conditions. These fibers enable the measurement of strains in the FRP wrapping. Additionally, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) is utilized as a well-established measurement technique. DIC allows for the precise measurement of displacements, rotations, and surface strains during the experiments. Together, these measurement techniques provide comprehensive data for analyzing the behavior of the joints under various loading conditions.

Medium-scale 90° X-joints under monotonic tensile loading

Custom-made eyeplates, machined from 42CrMo4 material, are used to connect to the flanges of the specimen. These eyeplates are fastened to the flanges using 16 prestressed M20 12.9 bolts, ensuring secure and robust connections. The eyeplates are designed with pin connections, allowing them to be pinned to the hinges. The hydraulic jack at the top and the concrete floor at the bottom serve as the support for the hinges, as depicted in Figure 3b.

To accurately measure the applied loads, a 2.5MN load cell is mounted between the hydraulic jack and the hinge. This load cell enables precise monitoring of the forces exerted on the joint throughout the experiments. By incorporating these components and measurement devices, the experimental setup ensures reliable load measurement and proper fixation of the joint for accurate testing and analysis.

Furthermore, the geometry of each specimen, particularly the alignment of the braces, is thoroughly inspected using advanced 3D scanning techniques with the Handyscan Black Elite from Creaform. This verification process ensures that the alignment of the braces falls within tolerance limits of 0.5°, effectively preventing any significant bending in the joint due to misalignment.

Medium-scale 90° X-joints under monotonic bending and multi-axial loading

The experimental setup involves the installation of a custom-made base plate and top plate, which are securely attached to the Hexapod traverse and pedestal, respectively, using prestressed rods. To ensure a reliable connection, the specimen flanges are then mounted onto the base and top plates using 16 prestressed M20 12.9 bolts per flange.

For the measurement of axial loads and bending moments, load cells are strategically placed within the legs of the pedestal, located within the main Hexapod structure. These load cells accurately capture the axial forces exerted in each leg. Following data transformation, the measured forces are expressed in the six directions corresponding to the machine axis system at the top of the specimen.

The control software of the testing machine defines the application of displacements and rotation at the top of the specimen, which is then internally converted to jack displacements.

Figure 2 a). 6-meter-high tensile loading frame 2.5MN; b). Photo medium-scale 90° X joint installation; c). Main hexapod and internal hexapod overview; d). Mounted specimen in Hexapod.

Measurement set-up

The experimental setup incorporates 3D GOM Aramis adjustable systems, which consist of two 12-megapixel cameras. For the uniaxial tensile experiments, one system is used, while for uniaxial bending out and in-plane, axial tension + bending out-of-plane load cases, two systems are employed. In the case of axial tension + bending out-of-plane + bending in-plane load cases, three systems are utilized. The measuring volume for all experiments is set at 1290 x 945 x 945 mm³.

During uniaxial experiments, the DIC system is positioned directly in front of the joint specimen. However, when experiments are conducted in the Hexapod setup, the systems are strategically placed to capture two or three quadrants of the joint, as depicted in Figure 3a. The 3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique, is utilized to indirectly identify debonding between the steel and FRP by measuring surface strains, suggested by He and Pavlovic (2022). DIC technique also enables the precise capture of global deformations, thereby eliminating any deformations originating from the experimental setups, resulting in accurate load-displacement or bending-rotation curves.

To enhance the accuracy of debonding area quantification, a distributed optical fiber measuring technique is employed in the experimental campaign. Specifically, the Luna ODISI 6000 system (Incorporated, 2023) is combined with polyamide-coated glass fibers. These optical fibers are embedded within the composite wrap near the interface, following the prescribed pattern illustrated in Figure 3b. This technique allows for more precise and detailed measurements of the debonding area within the joint.

Particularly, as the thickness of the composite wrapping increases, the conventional measuring technique using DIC may become less accurate due to through-thickness shear strain effects. In such cases, strain measurements obtained from the embedded optical fibers can provide valuable insights. The proximity of these fibers to the surface enables the detection of changes in the strain field caused by debonding, allowing for the identification of damage (Grave et al., 2015)

Figure 3 a). DIC setup for bending and multi-axial experiments; b). Optical fiber pattern embedded in medium-scale 90° X-joints.

Loading conditions

The experimental campaign encompasses five distinct loading conditions: uniaxial tension, uniaxial bending out and in-plane, axial tension + bending out-of-plane, and axial tension + bending out-of-plane + bending in-plane. In all experiments, deformation control is employed, with one degree of freedom (DOF) controlled for uniaxial cases and two or three DOFs controlled for multi-axial cases.

The X-joint configuration and capacity of the Hexapod impose some design limitations on the multi-axial loading conditions. Figure 1 depicts the estimated failure envelope of the medium-scale wrapped 90° X-joint, the tensile capacity of Hexapod and the yield resistance of the CHS.

In the uniaxial tensile experiment, the jack's loading speed is set to 1.0 mm/min, resulting in a strain rate of 1.3 micro strain/second at the brace as observed by DIC. For all load cases, the average strain

rate at the brace is maintained constant, and the loading speed is adjusted accordingly. A summary of the controlled DOFs, applied loading, number of specimens, and loading speeds can be found in Figure 5.

To ensure consistent multi-axial loading conditions in the various load cases, a constant ratio is maintained between the translation speed in the z-direction and the rotation speed around the x and/or y-axis throughout the experiment. This ratio is determined by utilizing preliminary Finite Element Models (FEM), which verify that the combined loading response can be applied in the Hexapod. The objective is to achieve a loading condition that promotes the occurrence of debonding failure while limiting plastic deformation of the steel CHS.

Figure 4 Load conditions medium-scale 90° X joints.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 illustrates the load-deformation curves obtained from ten medium-scale 90° X-joints wrapped with composite material. Displacement in the z-direction and rotation angle measurements were acquired using 3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) to eliminate any distortions caused by the experimental setups.

The ductile behavior of the wrapped joints is influenced by several factors. Initially, the temporary adhesive used for aligning the steel sections fails, followed by the initiation of debonding, as indicated by annotations A and B in Figure 5. This sequence is consistent across all loading conditions. Under uniaxial tensile loading, debonding progresses until one brace is completely debonded. In the case of uniaxial bending out-of-plane, debonding continues until the plastic bending resistance of the CHS is fully utilized. At this point, significant plastic deformation initiates debonding from the wrapping end. The complete separation of the wrap end and steel CHS induces large tensile stresses in the circumferential direction, leading to composite cracking and ultimate failure.

While early damage initiation can be concerning for fatigue performance, recent research by Feng et al. (2023) that debonding crack growth in wrapped composite joints exhibits crack retardation. This means that the early initiation of damage will not compromise the fatigue life of the joint. Therefore, it can be concluded that the presence of debonding cracks in the early stages will not have a detrimental effect on the overall fatigue performance of the joint.

Uniaxial bending in-plane exhibits a different failure sequence compared to out-of-plane bending. Shortly after the onset of non-linear behavior, a visible crack appears on the surface at the corner of the brace and chord sections. As the crack propagates, the joint resistance increases steadily until plastic deformation occurs in the steel CHS. After the crack has fully propagated, the resistance decreases.

Under axial tension + bending out-of-plane loading, debonding is the dominant failure mode, showing significantly more debonding compared to uniaxial out-of-plane bending. No initiation of steel yielding is observed, and the final failure is primarily caused by extensive debonding of the brace, where tensile strains are highest. Similar to uniaxial out-of-plane bending, tensile stresses in the circumferential direction lead to composite cracking as the ultimate failure mode.

In axial tension + bending out-of-plane + bending in-plane load cases, a similar trend is observed as in axial tension + bending out-of-plane loading. The difference is that for Axial+Mop+Mip loading, the ratio between axial tension (Axial) and bending moments (Mop and Mip) is smaller, indicating a greater influence of bending behavior. Similar to uniaxial bending out-of-plane and axial tension + bending out-of-plane, significant debonding is observed. Failure occurs due to composite cracking induced by high tensile stresses around the circumference after substantial debonding has occurred. Figure 6 provides an overview of the final failure modes for each loading condition.

Optical fiber strain measurements have proven to be an effective tool for detecting areas of debonding. In Figure 8, strain measurements along the fiber are presented, specifically between 1.62m and 1.87m as depicted in Figure 4b. These measurements were taken during in-plane loading at point B, where non-linearity is initiated. By scaling the strain values to a load level where no debonding has occurred (22kNm), changes in the strain distribution at higher load levels can be observed. At a load level of 55kNm, a noticeable increase in the scaled strain values is observed between 1.80m and 1.85m. This significant change in strain distribution indicates potential debonding occurring within that specific region.

Experimental results wrapped medium-scale 90° X-joints

Figure 5 a). Axial tension vs displacement in the z-direction of the top flange; b). Bending moment vs angle of the top flange around the x or y-axis.

Figure 6 Pictures of failure modes for; a), tensile loading (Axial), b). uni-axial bending out-of-plane (Mop), c). uni-axial bending in-plane (Mip), d). axial tension + bending out-of-plane, e). axial tension + bending out-of-plane + bending in-plane.

As mentioned in the introduction, the experimental results obtained will play a crucial role in calibrating finite element (FE) prediction models aimed at accurately estimating the ultimate capacity of the wrapped joint when subjected to combined loading conditions. In conjunction with the experimental data and FE simulations, an interaction criterion will be developed, following a similar approach as utilized in (NEN, 2011) which is derived from (Hoadley et al., 1985).

By conducting comprehensive numerical analyses, it becomes possible to establish the failure envelope for medium-scale 90° X-joints wrapped with composite materials, as illustrated in Figure 7. This failure envelope serves as a valuable tool for understanding the joint's behavior and determining its ultimate capacity under various loading scenarios.

Figure 7 Estimated failure envelop wrapped medium-scale 90° X-joints Multi-axial loading

Figure 8 Optical fibre strain measurements from 1.62m to 1.87m, as shown in Figure 3b. Scale stage = 22 [kNm], displayed stage = 55 [kNm]

CONCLUSION

The present study represents a significant milestone as the first experimental investigation of wrapped composite medium-scale 90° X-joints subjected to monotonic multi-axial load conditions. The scaled-down experiments encompassed a range of static loading conditions, including uni-axial tension, uni-axial bending out-of-plane, uni-axial bending in-plane, axial tension + bending out-of-plane, and axial tension + bending out-of-plane + bending in-plane, conducted using a Hexapod. By addressing the research gap pertaining to the multi-axial load behavior of wrapped joints, this research contributes to their application in wind and wave-exposed offshore multi-membered structures.

Remarkable bending resistance was observed in the composite wrap, reaching 100% of the plastic bending resistance of the steel circular hollow section ($\phi 168.3 \times 12.5 \text{ mm}$) and exhibiting substantial rotation capacity prior to final failure.

The experimental findings establish a consistent failure sequence for wrapped joints under different loading conditions. Debonding initiates at the brace-FRP interface and progressively extends towards the wrapping end. Although the final failure mode differs between tensile and bending-dominated load conditions, the study indicates that multi-axial loading does not significantly alter the failure modes, thereby confirming the wrapped joint's resilience in such scenarios.

The utilization of embedded optical fibers allowed for the capture of strain data near the interface, facilitating a comprehensive analysis of joint behavior. Optical fiber strain measurements effectively identified debonded regions, revealing a change in strain distributions at higher load levels, indicative of debonding occurrence.

Overall, this study demonstrates the superior performance of wrapped medium-scale 90° X-joints, emphasizing their resistance to static multi-axial loading. The findings contribute to the understanding of the structural behavior of these joints, providing valuable insights for their design and application in offshore structures. Future research can focus on further refining prediction models and exploring the fatigue performance of wrapped joints under complex loading conditions.

CITATIONS

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.